

On the phylogenetic significance of the aplacophoran Mollusca

Sobre la significación filogenética de los moluscos aplacoforos

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ABSTRACT

The increase in our knowledge of the organisation of the aplacophoran Mollusca over the last decades is outlined and the arguments with respect to their systematic position and phylogenetic significance are discussed.

First, the analysis of the mantle cavity in Neomeniomorpha and Chaetodermomorpha reveals an independent evolutionary transformation of both: in neomeniomorphs by a lateral narrowing of the mucociliary-gliding body with internalisation of the (posterior) mantle grooves, in chaetodermomorphs by a terminal shift and inversion of the (posterior) mantle grooves and the reduction of the foot to burrow in sediment, with midventral fusion of the mantle rims from posterior to anterior (HOFFMAN, 1949). This confirms their diphyletic status derived from a common ancestral group; together with the absence of true synapomorphies, this allows the chaetodermomorphs to be separated as a proper clade Caudofoveata (Boettger, 1956) in contrast to the neomeniomorph aplacophorans or Solenogastres.

Second, the comparison of the alimentary tract and the excretory system in both classes with those in the monophyletic Testaria (Placophora + Conchifera) contradicts an origin of the aplacophoran Mollusca by regressive derivation from Placophora (as assumed by Pelseneer, 1890); rather, it confirms the conservative level of the aplacophoran organisation, which is also strongly supported by cladistic analysis.

Third, the mantle cover, the musculature, and the elaboration of the alimentary tract reflect a gradual anagenesis within Mollusca from the aplacophoran to the polyplacophoran and mono-placophoran (conchiferan) levels.

Fourth, within the Mollusca the Solenogastres have retained a primitive stage of the radula which, in its most conservative level, appears to be characterized by the monoserial type (median bars or two teeth with symphysis). In correlation with the cnidaria-vory in Solenogastres, a molluscan origin from ciliary-gliding, mesenchymate Spiralia is accepted, and the plesiomorphic conditions of molluscan characters are outlined.

RESUMEN

Se pone de manifiesto el mayor conocimiento sobre la organización de los moluscos aplacóforos en las últimas décadas y se discuten su posición sistemática y relevancia filogenética.

El análisis de la cavidad del manto en Neomeniomorpha y Chaetodermomorpha revela una transformación evolutiva independiente en ambos grupos: en el primero por un adelgazamiento lateral del cuerpo mucociliar con internalización de los pliegues posteriores

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del manto, en los Chaetodermomorpha por un cambio terminal e inversión de los pliegues posteriores del manto y la reducción del pie para enterrarse en el sedimento, con una fusión ventral de los bordes del manto de atrás adelante (HOFFMAN, 1949). Esto confirma su estatus difilético a partir de un ancestro común. Junto con la ausencia de verdaderas sinatopomorfías, esto permite separar a los Chaetodermomorpha como verdaderos Caudofoveata (Boettger, 1956) en contraste con los Solenogastres.

La comparación del tracto alimentario y el sistema excretor en ambas clases con las de los Testaria (Placophora y Conchifera) contradice un posible origen de los aplacóforos por derivación regresiva de los Plocophora (tal y como sugirió Pelseneer, 1890); esto confirma el nivel conservativo de la organización aplacófora, lo cual se sostiene también por análisis cladístico.

La cubierta del manto, la musculatura y la elaboración del tracto alimentario refleja una anagénesis gradual dentro de los moluscos, desde los aplacóforos a los poliplacóforos y los conchífera.

Dentro de los moluscos, los solenogastros han conservado un estadio primitivo de rádula que, en sus niveles más conservativos, es del tipo monoserial (piezas medias o dos dientes con sínfisis). En correlación con los solenogastros comedores de cnidarios, se acepta un origen a partir de Spiralia mesenquimáticos con desplazamiento ciliar, y se indican las condiciones plesiomórficas de los caracteres de moluscos.

KEY WORDS: *Aplacophora*, Solenogastres, Caudofoveata, molluscan phylogeny.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Aplacophora*, Solenogastres, Caudofoveata, filogenia de moluscos.

INTRODUCTION

The purely marine aplacophoran molluscs are classified in two taxa, the chaetodermomorphs or Caudofoveata and the neomeniomorphs or Solenogastres (Fig. 1), known since 1845 (*Chaetoderma*: Lovén) and 1875 (*Neomenia*: Tullberg), respectively. A first period of enlargement in knowledge began in 1877 and stretched to 1921, with the description of many new species of both chaetodermatids and neomeniids (mainly Koren and Danielssen, Hubrecht, Kowalevsky and Marion, Pruvot, Wirén, Thiele, Nierstrasz, Heath, Odhner; see SIMROTH, 1893b, HOFFMANN, 1929). A second period may be outlined from 1938-1950, with investigations by Baba, Stork, Leloup, Hoffman and Schwabl (see FISCHER-PIETTE AND FRANC, 1960, HYMAN, 1967); a third period began in 1967 involving L. v. Salvini-Plawen and since 1972 likewise A. Scheltema. Overviews and compilations of organisation are given by SALVINI-PLAWEN (1971, 1972a, 1985) and SCHELTEMA, TSCHERKASSKY AND

KUZIRIAN (1994). Most of these investigations concern organisational diversity based on descriptions of species, but comprehensive collections still await elaboration. Due to the habitat of members of both the chaetodermomorphs/Caudofoveata and the neomeniomorphs/Solenogastres (mostly below 40 meters depth) living observations, biological data and physiological investigations are still rare. However, the work over the last decades has contributed considerably to elucidating the systematic position of the aplacophorans and to underlining their phylogenetic significance.

Scientific results in the phylogenetic context suffer from two properties: they are often evaluated one-sidedly in relation to a predominant or central group (for molluscs: gastropods or conchiferans in general), and there is an inflexible trend to press them into some beloved theory (e.g. molluscs as altered coelomates or even articulates) rather than to adapt or reject hypotheses based on new

Figure 1. Aplacophoran Mollusca. External aspect of an animal (Solenogastres: *Nematomenia banyulensis*; Caudofoveata: *Falcidens sagittiferus*), and organisational sketch of alimentary tract, gono-pericardial system and mantle cavity. cg: cerebral ganglion; go: gonad; md: glandular duct; mg: midgut; mgs: unpaired midgut sack; mt: spawning duct (internalised mucous tract of mantle groove); pc: pericardium; pg: pedal gland; ps: pedal shield; so: dorsoterminal or osphradial sense organ.

Figura 1. Moluscos Aplacóforos. Aspecto exterior de un animal (Solenogastres: *Nematomenia banyulensis*; Caudofoveata: *Falcidens sagittiferus*), y esquema de la organización del tracto digestivo, del sistema gono-pericárdico y de la cavidad paleal. cg: ganglio cerebral; go: gónada; md: conducto glandular; mg: intestino medio; mgs: saco impar del intestino medio; mt: conducto del desove (tracto mucoso internalizado del surco paleal); pc: pericardio; pg: glándula pedal; ps: escudo pedal; so: órgano sensorial dorsoterminal u osfradial.

facts and results. The aplacophoran molluscs, as two small, conservative taxa, additionally suffer from the great effort and expense to collect them. Our standard of knowledge is therefore weak compared with other molluscan groups. They are thus often not seriously considered in comparative evaluations, be it due to their low number, be it that the "a-placophoran" condition suggests a regressive state, or be it that they are regarded as aberrant inconveniences that are not equivalent to "true" molluscs.

1. THE DIPHYLY/PARAPHYLY OF *APLACOPHORA *

The two aplacophoran taxa exhibit a dorsal integument (mantle) with calcareous (aragonitic) products, a mantle cavity with body outlets, a radula, a tetra-neurous nervous system, and a gono-pericardium including a heart that performs open circulation and ultrafiltration. In spite of their unfamiliar appearance they are thus true Mollusca. Additional characters in each of the two groups unequivocally confirm them as members of the phylum.

When IHERING (1876) created (within Amphineura) the Aplacophora in contrast to Placophora, he emphasized the different organisation of Chaetodermatidae and Neomeniidae from chitons. GEGENBAUR (1878: 139) proposed for the group which has "a more distinct separation of the ventral side through the differentiation of a furrow", the name Solenogastres; unfortunately and misleadingly he also included *Chaetoderma* based on the erroneous description by GRAFF (1877) of the dorsoterminal sense organ as the vestige of a ventral furrow. As early as 1883, Lankester classified Neomeniae and *Chaetoderma* as equivalent orders to Polyplacophora within his Isopleura. In Lankester's Treatise, PELSENEER (1906) again grouped his orders Neomeniomorpha and Chaetodermomorpha below Aplacophora, a classification that has been retained by many authors up to present. Decisive insights, however, were presented by HOFFMAN (1949). His detailed histological, comparative investigation on the mantle cavities of *Chaetoderma nitidulum* Loven, 1845, *Proneomenia "antarctica"* (= *Dorymenia hoffmani* S.-Plawen, 1978) and *Leptochiton asellus* (Gmelin, 1791) revealed the diphyletic status of recent aplacophorans (Fig. 2). The posterior mantle grooves in lower representatives of the (secondarily much flattened) Placophora are provided with mucous tracts as well as with the outlets of gonoducts and excretory organs (Fig. 2A); these tracts parallel in extension at least the merobranchiate elaboration of ctenidia. This paired section of the mantle cavity in the ctenidia-less neomeniomorphs/Solenogastres is represented by the glandular spawning ducts (also known as shell glands or "lower gonoducts"). Consequently, as in other molluscs, the mesodermal pericardioducts open directly into the ectodermal mantle cavity, i.e. here into the internalised mucous tracts or spawning ducts (Fig. 2B). This condition is clearly evidenced also in juvenile specimens, in which the anlagen of the pericardioducts come from the mesodermal pericardium and the anlagen of the spawn-

ing ducts emerge from the ectodermal mantle cavity rudiment (cf. e.g. BABA, 1938 for *Epimения babai* S.-Plawen, 1997, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978 for *Neomenia laminata* S.-Plawen, 1978, or TODT AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2003 for *Spionemia prematura*).

In contrast, in chaetodermomorphs/Caudofoveata the mucous tracts of the posterior mantle grooves as well as the ctenidia (one pair) are retained as free structures; here, however, they are arranged upside down ventrally in the mantle cavity (HOFFMAN, 1949). In addition, the pericardioducts are not directly connected to the (mucous tracts of the) mantle cavity; rather, they each lead out into a pair of voluminous glandular organs of unknown homology (see below); only these glandular ducts or sacks open lateroventrally into the mucous tracts (Fig. 2C). Both the arrangement of the mucous tracts (present in all females, rarely in males) and the position of those openings demonstrate an inversion of the organs (HOFFMAN, 1949). Thus, the mantle cavity configurations of neomeniomorphs and chaetodermomorphs are clearly different from each other. In neomeniomorphs they reflect an evolutive slendering of their forerunners: the ciliary-gliding body narrows, with the foot becoming a mere pedal groove, and the (posterior) mantle grooves internalise to become the present spawning ducts. In contrast, the precursors of the chaetodermomorphs — as sediment burrowers — underwent a terminal shift of the (posterior) mantle grooves and a ventral fusion of the mantle rims into a tube (cf. Scaphopoda); this included an inversion of the mucous tracts and ctenidia. This development was paralleled by the reduction of the foot with midventral fusion of the mantle rims from posterior to anterior (see the midventral anterior mantle suture in some *Scutopus* species). The result was a cylindrical, worm-like habit.

These scenarios clearly reflect two totally different evolutionary processes: neither can the chaetodermomorph

Figure 2. Relation of pericardium, pericardioducts and mantle cavity in A Placophora (with ctenidia), B Solenogastres and C female Caudofoveata (with ctenidia). At left schematic views from lateral, at right schematic views projected from behind according to oblique cross sections indicated at left. go: gonad; md: glandular duct; ml: musculus longitudinalis; mt: mucous tract of mantle groove; pc: pericardium; so: osphradial sense organ.

Figura 2. Relación del pericardio, de los pericardioductos y de la cavidad paleal en A Placophora (con ctenidios), B Solenogastres y C Caudofoveata femeninos (con ctenidios). A la izquierda vistas esquemáticas de lateral, a la derecha vistas esquemáticas por atrás según las secciones transversales indicadas. go: gónada; md: conducto glandular; ml: musculus longitudinalis; mt: tracto mucoso del surco paleal; pc: pericardio; so: órgano sensorio osfradial.

Figure 3. Structures of ventral body adjacent to mantle rim in A Caudofoveata (region of pedal shield), B Solenogastres (region of spawning ducts / mucous tracts), C Placophora (region of mucous tracts) (after SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991). ce: microvillious epithelium of mantle groove; cu: irregularly-arranged microvilli within matrix of glyco-calix; ml: musculus longitudinalis; mr: mantle rim (inner mantle fold); mt: mucous tract of mantle groove; ps1: pedal shield (cerebrally innervated); ps2: pedal sole (ventrally innervated); sg: glands of pedal shield or sole.

Figura 3. Estructuras del cuerpo ventral contiguo al margen del manto A en Caudofoveata (región del escudo pedal), B en Solenogastres (región de los tractos mucosos / conductos de desove), C en Placophora (región de los tractos mucosos) (según SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991). ce: epitelio microvillosa del surco paleal; cu: estrato de glyco-calix con microvilli irregulares; ml: musculus longitudinalis; mr: margen del manto (pliegue interior del manto); mt: tracto mucoso del surco paleal; ps1: escudo pedal (de innervación cerebral); ps2: suela pedal (de innervación ventral); sg: glándulas del escudo pedal o de la suela pedal.

configuration be derived from the neomeniomorph conditions, nor vice versa (see Fig. 2). Both arrangements are comprehensible only when each derived from ancestors whose posterior body bore a peripedal mantle groove with mucous tracts and the outlets of the pericardioducts. Such a relation of the two aplacophoran groups clearly reflects a diphyly (or, including the more flattened Placophora, a triphyly). Thus, BOETTGER (1956) separated the chaetodermomorphs as Caudofoveata from other, neomeniomorph aplacophorans with a pedal groove: *Ventroplicida* (Boettger, 1956) = Solenogastres (Gegenbaur, 1878, emend. SIMROTH, 1893a). SALVINI-PLAWEN (1967) finally accepted both as independent classes equivalent to Placophora. Are there synapomorphies of one of these classes with the Placophora (or other molluscan group)? Up to the present no conclusion can be drawn about whether — within paraphyletic aplacophorans — the Caudofoveata or the Solenogastres are, from the cladistic point of view, the sister-group of Placophora. Referring to

the Solenogastres, we may assume that their precursors were likewise provided with antero-lateral mantle grooves that underwent regression during evolutive transformation (HOFFMAN, 1949). This is supported by the presence of a pedal gland, which suggests a former separation of the cerebrally innervated perioral region (snout, “head”-portion) from the ventrally innervated foot with pedal gland. This would equalise the atrial sense organ or vestibulum of Solenogastres with the pre-oral mantle groove (HOFFMAN, 1949). On the other hand, it is not clear whether such precursors were already provided with ctenidia (see below). In contrast, at present we cannot advance similar assumptions about the regression of mantle grooves in Caudofoveata. They show no vestige of a pedal gland, and consequently we do not know whether the mantle grooves of their flattened ancestors also extended into the anterior body. The post- to peri-oral, secondarily cuticularised buccal plate or pedal shield reflects a histology and configuration similar to that of the pedal groove in

Figure 4. Innervation areas in the ventral anterior body (with identical marking) of A Caudofoveata, B Solenogastres, C Placophora. as: atrial sense organ; cg: cerebral ganglion; eg: esophageal gland; fs: foot (pedal sole); hs: head plate; mc: anterior mantle groove; mg: midgut; nsl: lateral nerve cord; nsv: ventral nerve cord; oe: esophagus; pf: peri-oral fold (snout); pg: pedal gland; ps: pedal shield; vfg: ventral foregut gland.

Figura 4. Areas de inervación del cuerpo anterior ventral (marcadas idénticamente) en A Caudofoveata, B Solenogastres, C Placophora. as: órgano sensitivo atrial; cg: ganglio cerebral; eg: glándula esofágica; fs: pie (suela pedal); hs: cabeza; mc: surco paleal anterior; mg: intestino medio; nsl: cordón nervioso lateral; nsv: cordón nervioso ventral; oe: esófago; pf: hocico; pg: glándula pedal; ps: escudo pedal; vfg: glándula ventral de la faringe.

Solenogastres and the foot in Placophora (HOFFMAN, 1949, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a; Fig. 3); the fine structural organisation (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991, SCHELTEMA ET AL., 1994) neither supports nor contradicts the suggestion that the shield might be derived from an anterior portion of the ancestral foot. Yet, the pedal shield is cerebrally innervated (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a; Fig. 4), and it could therefore be interpreted to represent the remnant of a formerly more extended (ventrally and cerebrally innervated) ventral locomotory organ (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a, 1981a); the mantle grooves in such case were restricted to the postero-lateral body.

Despite these as yet unsettled conditions regarding the configuration of the common ancestral anterior body (no organogenesis known in Caudofoveata), the different organisation of the posterior body in the two groups (mantle cavity; Fig. 2) unequivocally demonstrates the diphyly of Solenogastres and Caudofoveata. That diphyly is also strongly evidenced by cladistic analysis, which either proposes a paraphyly of aplacophorans with (dependent on character choice and coding) the Solenogastres or the Caudofoveata as first offshoot (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996, HASZPRUNAR, 2000), or results in a compromise-polytomy (triphly) of Solenogastres, Caudofoveata and Placophora (which in strict Hennigian cladistics always includes a not yet solved paraphyly). To date there are no comparative data from molecular sequences to give support to one or the other side: The available 18S rDNA sequence of *Scutopus* (Caudofoveata) clusters in midst of the Mollusca (WINNEPENINCKS, BACKELJAU AND DE WACHTER, 1996); attempts at sequencing the 18S rDNA gene of three different species of Solenogastres merely identified gut contents as diverse Cnidaria (Dr. Hermann Dreyer, Wien, unpublished), a result also obtained by other investigators (pers. comm.; see also WINNEPENINCKS ET AL., 1996); probably only DNA sequences of non-feeding larvae might provide valuable information. Polytomy is thus presently preferred, being supported by

the manifold differences in the organisation between the three groups (e.g. SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a, 1985; see Table I). Diphyly of recent aplacophoran molluscs is even strikingly evident in "monophyletic" representations (SCHELTEMA, 1978, SCHELTEMA ET AL., 1994), with their separate treatment of organ systems of each group. Finally, besides the sexual condition (hermaphroditism in Solenogastres), the single preoral ciliary trochus in larvae of Solenogastres also contrasts to the three preoral trochi in *Scutopus* and *Chaetoderma* (Caudofoveata; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991, NIELSEN, 1995) as well as in other groups (OKUSU, 2002).

Paraphyly of *Aplacophorans* with diphyly of recent groups is in accordance with the (prerequisite) lack of true synapomorphies (in contrast to SCHELTEMA, 1996, IVANOV, 1996). The mantle cover of cuticle and unicellularly formed aragonitic sclerites, likewise elaborated at the girdle/perinotum of Placophora (HOFFMAN, 1949, HAAS, 1981), represents a plesiomorphic character, as does the lack of excretory organs (excretoria) for the secondary urine in aplacophoran organisation (see below). The so-called ganglionated nervous system is only present in the Solenogastres: They mostly possess medullary ventral and lateral body cords combined with more or less distinctly outlined, fairly serial ganglia; all stages between a predominantly medullary condition and a true separation of carya into ganglia interconnected by pure fibrous portions have been observed. In Caudofoveata, however, the medullary system shows only a few ganglia (buccal ganglia, large ventral ganglion at the beginning ventral cords, precerebral ganglia; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a); this reflects a similar condition in Placophora (buccal and subradular ganglia). Thus, in contrast to Solenogastres, no ganglionisation of body cords can be stated in Caudofoveata. The originally paired osphradial sense organ is also clearly a molluscan plesiomorphy (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981a, HASZPRUNAR, 1987). The position of the latter in Caudofoveata is at the dorsal border of

Table I. Comparison of characters in Solenogastres, Caudofoveata and Placophora.
Tabla I. Comparación entre los caracteres de Solenogastres, Caudofoveata y Placophora.

Character	Solenogastres	Caudofoveata	Placophora
Chitinous cuticle	present	present	present
Mantle sclerites	scales, spicules	scales	scales at girdle
Foot	groove with folds	reduced	large foot
Pedal gland	present	no gland	present in larvae
Cerebral portion	mouth/snout+ atrium	mouth + buccal/pedal shield	head disc+anterior groove
Osphradial sense organ	at dorsoterminal mantle area	at dorsoterminal mantle border	within mantle cavity
Ctenidia	no ctenidia	one pair	5-88 pairs
Mucous tracts of mantle cavity	internalised	free, upside down	free, at roof
"Lower gonoducts" of literature	part of mantle cavity (spawning ducts/mucous tracts)	"glandular ducts" between pericardioducts and mantle cavity	distal portion of proper gonoducts
Excretory organ (emunctoria)	no emunctoria	function assumed by "glandular ducts"?	central portion of pericardioducts
Outlet of gonads	gono-pericardioducts	gono-pericardioducts	gonoducts
Body wall musculature	present, only below mantle	present, ventrally fused below mantle	vestigial, only below mantle
<i>M. longitudinalis</i>	present	vestigially present	present (?)
Bundles of dorso-ventral musculature	serially arranged	serial, but vestigial	16 pairs
Nervous system	ganglionated	medullary	medullary
Latero-terminal commissure	supra-rectal	supra-rectal	supra-rectal
Subradular organ	not present	not present	present
Radula membrane	no separate pre-ribbon	separate pre-ribbon	separate ribbon
Radula	monoserial-distichous, polystichous-polyserial	distichous	polystichous in paired anlage
Radula support	very simple to complex with turgescent cells	two compact bolsters	two vesicles with cartilages
Ventral foregut glandular organs	paired follicles to elaborate organs	paired follicles	vestigial pouches of subradular sack
Anterior midgut	body-filling	body filling	narrow esophagus + stomach + glands
Posterior midgut	body-filling	midgut duct+ midgut sack	narrowed to looped intestine
Heart (ventricle)	invagination of pericardium	in part invagination of pericardium	invagination of pericardium
Aorta	no aorta	present	present
Sex	hermaphroditism	separate sexes	mostly separate sexes
Sperm	derived introsperms	modified aquasperms	modified aquasperms
Larval type	pericalymma, stenocalymma	stenocalymma	pseudo-trochophora
Preoral trochi of larvae	one	three	one or two
Locomotion	muco-ciliary gliding	burrowing	muco-ciliary gliding
Nutrition	carnivory	micro-omnivory	predominantly herbivory

the mantle cavity and in Solenogastres dorsally outside the mantle cavity (in *Neomenia labrosa* S.-Plawen, 1978, the position is likewise outside the retracted mantle cavity: misinterpretation by IVANOV, 1996). This dorsoterminal loca-

tion is different in detail and is thus too ambivalent to serve as a good synapomorphy. This also holds true for the gonopericardioducts (paired interconnection between gonads and pericardium) in both aplacophoran groups.

Figure 5. Regionated alimentary tract of Testaria (Placophora + Conchifera) (after MIZZARO-WIMMER AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001). (cr): crop (Conchifera only); dfg: salivary gland(s); eg: esophageal gland; ep: esophageal pouch; in: intestine; (j): jaw (Conchifera only); mg: midgut gland; mo: mouth opening; oe: esophagus; ph: pharynx; pp: pharyngeal pouch; ras: radula sheath; re: rectum; sro: subradular organ; (ss): style sack (Conchifera only); st: stomach; vfg: ventral foregut gland(s).

Figura 5. Tracto digestivo subdividido de los Testaria, (según MIZZARO-WIMMER Y SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001). (cr): papo (solo Conchifera); dfg: glándula(s) salivar(es); eg: glándula esofágica; ep: bolsa esofágica; in: intestino delgado; (j): mandíbula (solo Conchifera); mg: glándula del intestino medio; mo: boca; oe: esófago; ph: faringe; pp: bolsa faríngea; ras: bolsa de odontoblastos; re: recto; sro: órgano subradular; (ss): saco del estilo (sólo Conchifera); st: estomago; vfg: glándula(s) ventral(es) de la faringe.

This condition either is a retained pleiomorphy of pre-testarian configuration, or it represents a paedomorphy (as convergent apomorphy or synapomorphy?). Based on the different evolutive transformation of the posterior body (see above), it may also reflect true autapomorphies in both Caudofoveata and Solenogastres (see below, chapt. 6).

2. MIDGUT AND EMUNCTORIA

A comprehensive analysis of the digestive systems in Mollusca (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981b, 1988a) demonstrates two principal configurations of the postradular alimentary tract: either a simple, basically body-filling midgut (*Aplacophora*^{*}; Fig 1), or a midgut axially regionated into oesophagus with paired glandular pouch, stomach with paired digestive gland, and a narrowed, wound to enrolled intestine (Testaria; Fig. 5). The detailed coincidence of the organ system between Placophora and conservative Conchifera also includes the subradular organ, the radular bolster, the anterior oesophagus with dorsal food channel and the simple posterior esophagus (SALVINI-PLAWEN 1988a). All these clearly synapomorphic

elaborations in Placophora and Conchifera define the monophyletic Testaria (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a, 1985, 1991; WINGSTRAND, 1985).

In contrast, the Solenogastres possess a through-going, uniformly body-filling midgut (middorsally confined by the gonads) without regionation. The Caudofoveata show a basically similar midgut, yet with a posterior splitting into midgut sack and midgut duct ("intestine"). This latter exit canal is an asymmetrically dorsal-right, longitudinal subdivision of the posterior midgut, leaving the main portion as a single, voluminous blind sack (Fig. 1). As demonstrated elsewhere (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981b, 1988a), this longitudinal splitting is evidenced by the most conservatively represented configuration in some members of the Limifossoridae [e.g. *Psilodens elongatus* (S.-Plawen, 1972)]: in these the undivided (anterior) midgut and the midgut sack still exhibit an identical histological elaboration, thus still forming a histological entity. Terminally, the midgut duct continues in the ventrally inclined hindgut to open at the bottom of the mantle cavity. Thus, in contrast to the Testaria (Fig. 5), in which the midgut glands principally are a paired lateral pouching of the stomach

Figure 6. Gono-pericardial system of Testaria (Placophora + Conchifera) (after MIZZARO-WIMMER AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001). ao: aorta; aob: bulb of aorta; at: heart auricle; em: emunctorium (excretory organ); exd: lower pericardioduct or excretory duct ("ureter"); exs: excretory sack; gd: gonoduct; gdg: gonoduct gland; go: gonad; gpd: gono-pericardial interconnection; pc: pericardium; pd: upper pericardioduct ("reno"-pericardial canal); ve: ventricle.

Figura 6. Sistema gono-pericárdico de los Testaria (según MIZZARO-WIMMER Y SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001). ao: aorta; aob: bulbo del aorta; at: aurícula; em: emunctorio (órgano excretor); exd: conducto excretor; exs: saco excretorio; gd: gonoducto; gdg: glándula del gonoducto; go: gónada; gpd: comunicación gono-pericárdica; pc: pericardio; pd: pericardioducto proximal (canal reno-pericárdico); ve: ventrículo.

(central midgut region) and the intestine is a subsequent narrowed posterior midgut, in Caudofoveata both the midgut sack and the midgut duct ("intestine") together represent the posterior midgut. These midgut relations in Caudofoveata and Testaria therefore cannot be evaluated as being homologous, and a unifying taxon *Hepagastralia* (HASZPRUNAR 2000) consequently is misleading.

Though change in nourishment — such as from herbivory to carnivory — is followed by reorganising adaptations in the alimentary tract, such reorganisation towards carnivory merely involves a simplification of the existing configuration (with stomach, etc.). As demonstrated in several conchiferan groups (e.g. Cephalopoda, Scaphopoda, "Septibranchia"; cf. SALVINI-PLAWEN 1988a), however, the configuration itself remains unaltered and the genetic information for the regionated midgut of Testaria is not suppressed. Despite a regulative plasticity of the alimentary tract — in comparative view with cephalopods etc. — a reorganisation of

the midgut relations in Testaria-Placophora towards those in Solenogastres and/or Caudofoveata (PELSENEER, 1890) appears to be an out-dated speculation (see also NIERSTRASZ, 1910, and HOFFMANN, 1930). The main point is that the uniformly body-filling midgut of Solenogastres (and, longitudinally subdivided, of Caudofoveata) refers to a primary configuration rather than a regressive adaptation from a regionated testarian midgut.

The excretory system in Testaria typically performs two different functions. In Placophora and Conchifera a primary urine is produced by ultrafiltration through podocytes at the atrial heart epithelium (ØKLAND, 1980, 1982, ANDREWS, 1981, 1988, REYNOLDS, 1990). This primary urine is drained out of the pericardium by the pericardioducts ("renopericardial" canals). Here, the central portion of the two pericardioducts is elaborated to secrete solutes, to reabsorb organic molecules as well as to abstract resulting waste material. By an emunctorial process it produces the secondary urine and thus represents an

excretory organ ("kidney") or emunctorium, with the outleading lower pericardioduct — excretory duct or exit canal ("ureter") — opening into the mantle groove or cavity (Fig. 6). In Solenogastres, the production of the primary urine is likewise performed by the atrial heart epithelium (REYNOLDS, MORSE AND NORENBURG, 1993, MORSE AND REYNOLDS, 1996). In contrast to Testaria, however, the pericardioducts are simple, variably ciliated mesodermal outlets which open into the internalised mucous tract portions of the ectodermal mantle cavity (spawning ducts, see Figure 2); the pericardioducts exhibit no transformation into an excretory organ (emunctorium), and no secondary urine is produced.

In Caudofoveata the primary urine produced by the atrial heart epithelium (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND BARTOLOMAEUS, 1995) is drained by the ciliated pericardioducts into the voluminous glandular ducts, which, in turn, then open into the mantle cavity (Fig. 2). As the organogenesis and morphological significance of these glandular ducts or sacks are unknown (see below), no homology can be ascertained. Crystals or electron-dense vacuolated inclusions appear to be present in the cells of the glandular ducts (WIREN, 1892: 55; HEATH, 1911: 54 and 71; SCHELTEMA, 1978; Tscherkassky in SCHELTEMA *ET AL.*, 1994: Fig 23G), indicating potential formation of excretory products. Yet, these latter organs themselves ("coelomoducts" in SCHELTEMA, 1978, "lower gametoducts" in MORSE AND REYNOLDS, 1996) are not part of the pericardioducts (see below) and thus appear not to be homologous to emunctoria. At best, they could represent analogous organs autapomorphically adapted to an equivalent or similar excretory function in caudofoveate fore-runners.

The organisation of both organ systems clearly demonstrates that the axial regionation of the midgut as well as the elaboration of pericardioductal excretory organs in Testaria are evolutionary novelties (autapomorphies) that are not yet differentiated at the apla-

cophoran level; a postulated loss of excretory organs (SCHELTEMA, 1996 in contrast to IVANOV, 1996) is not supported by organogenesis (see above). On the other hand, the pallial position of the excretory organs outside the dorsoventral musculature in Tryblidia and Bivalvia (in contrast to Placophora; HASZPRUNAR AND SCHAEFER, 1997b) could be interpreted such that the elaboration of emunctoria is polyphyletic. Based on these and other arguments (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1988b, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND BARTOLOMAEUS, 1995), the excretory organs in Mollusca-Testaria, though functionally reflecting a so-called metanephridial system (RUPPERT AND SMITH, 1988), have organogenetically (morphologically) nothing to do with "metanephridia" (or "nephridia", "kidneys") of other animal groups. In order to avoid unjustified homologisations and for the sake of accuracy, the testarian organs should preferably be termed emunctoria (see HOFFMANN, 1934, 1937).

3. RADULA CONFIGURATIONS

The Solenogastres, with their retained conservative midgut, exhibit a remarkable diversity in the mantle characters, in the types of radula, and in the elaboration of the accessory genital organs. The conservative level of Solenogastres, classified according to their mantle cover as Pholidoskepia, is clearly reflected by a thin cuticle with solid, scaly sclerites. This conservative level is also evidenced by the same condition in Caudofoveata and Placophora (see below). The basal mantle configuration in Solenogastres, i.e. scales, is supported by the change of the primary scales to hollow spicules during metamorphosis in *Rhopalomenia aglaopheniae* (Kow. and Mar., 1887) and *Epimения babai* (Pruvot, 1892, OKUSU, 2002), both belonging to the advanced level of Cavi-belonia. Also, Pholidoskepia either possess poorly outlined ventral foregut glandular organs (comparable to those in Caudofoveata) or a paired duct with

Figure 7. EM cross section through left part of most anterior radula of *Wirenia argentea*, with dorsal tooth (ra above) and ventrally turned tooth (ra below), with interconnecting radular material (ic) forming symphysis to teeth of right side (photo: G. Haszprunar).

Figura 7. Corte al microscopio de la parte izquierda de la zona anterior de la rádula de Wirenia argentea, con el diente dorsal (ra, arriba) y el diente torcido ventralmente (ra, debajo), con material de interconexión (ic) formando una sínfisis con los dientes del lado derecho (fotografía G. Haszprunar).

subepithelial follicles (so-called type A), whereas among Cavibelonia — apart from organs of type A — four additional types are elaborated (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972b, 1978). With regard to the radula, Pholidoskepia possess either monoserial or biserial types, whereas Cavibelonia also have polyserial/polystichous radulae.

Investigations on biserial-distichous radulae in some species revealed particular conditions. PRUVOT (1900) points to the development of the distichous radula of *Pruvotina impexa* out of a monoserial anlage. SALVINI-PLAWEN (1978) describes the developmental sequence of the biserial radula of *Plawenia schizoradulata*: it begins with a symphysis (as a U-shaped, monoserial organ), which divides towards the pharynx to become truly biserial. SALVINI-PLAWEN (1988a) demonstrates

that the distichous radula of *Wirenia argentea* Odhner, 1921 (syn. *Aesthoherpia glandulosa* S.-Plawen) is interconnected by radular material forming a symphysis (Fig. 7), thus being in truth a monoserial organ without differentiating a real radular membrane (ribbon). In contrast, a basally separated membrane can light-optically be distinguished in *Caudofoveata* (SCHELTEMA, 1978, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981b, DEIMEL, 1982, SCHELTEMA ET AL., 1994). WOLTER (1992) confirms for the investigated Solenogastres (*Genitoconia* sp., *Wirenia argentea*, *Micromenia fodiens* (Schwabl, 1955) and a species of Cavibelonia) the lack of a real ribbon, but states that the *Caudofoveata* (*Scutopus robustus* S.-Plawen, 1970) likewise do not differentiate a true, separated radular membrane, but rather a type of pre-ribbon. The rudimentary ribbon in Solenogastres, however, is

attached to the basis of the teeth by microfibrils that extend into the underlying epithelium. These are lacking in Caudofoveata and Placophora, and the rudimentary membrane of Caudofoveata is linked to older teeth only by fibrillous bundles (WOLTER, 1992, SCHELTEMA *ET AL.*, 1994), as is the ribbon in Placophora. In connection with sclerotisation, this condition distinctly simulates in Caudofoveata a light-optically separated ribbon (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981b, Wolter, 1992).

All these conditions point to the fact that a monoserial radula, including the biserial-distichous radula with symphysis, represents the most conservative type, only retained in Solenogastres. This is also reflected by computer-processed analyses (see below), according to which the Solenogastres-Pholidoskepia with monoserial radulae represent the basal group. Nearly all Solenogastres are predators on Cnidaria (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981b), and they probably retained their conservative midgut due to their carnivorous habit. The different types of radulae (family characters) infer that most of these types are well-suited or even adapted for uptake of cnidarian food, particularly the monoserial and distichous types. Monoserial radulae (without symphysis) are elaborated in Dondersiidae, Macellomeniidae, and (?) Sandalomeniidae (all Pholidoskepia) as well as in Acanthomeniidae and Amphimeniidae (Cavibelonia) (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978). In several species, adaptation has led to a fused, unpaired outlet of the ventral foregut glandular organs associated with the radula. These include *Macellomenia* (3 spp.), *Stylomenia* (2 spp.), *Pholidoherpia* (2 spp.), *Sandalomenia?* (2 spp.), two species of *Micromenia* and *Dondersia festiva* Hubrecht, 1888. In contrast, other *Dondersia* (4 spp.), *Micromenia simplex* Leloup, 1948, *Nematomenia* (*N. flavens* (Pruvot, 1890) and at least five more species), *Lyratoherpia* (2 spp.), *Ichthyomenia ichthyodes* (Pruvot, 1890), *Heathia porosa* (Heath, 1911), Acanthomeniidae (3 spp.) and Amphimeniidae (23 spp.) still possess the paired outlet of

the glandular organs (e.g., PRUVOT, 1891, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978, SCHELTEMA, 1999, HANDL AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001, 2003). The distichous type (in general with paired outlet of glandular organs) among Pholidoskepia is elaborated in Gymnomeniidae, Lepidomeniidae and Meiomeniidae. The distichous-biserial type, however, is the predominant one among Solenogastres in general; in some members the radula sheath is even distinctly paired at its proximal end (e.g., *Pruvotina peniculata* in SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978, *Plawenia sphaera* in SCHELTEMA AND SCHANDER, 2000).

All Caudofoveata definitely possess a distichous radula, though they appear to be mainly micro-omnivores or micro-carnivores. In Chaetodermatidae this nourishment has led to a highly modified radula apparatus that is correlated to a kind of stomach region in the midgut with a protostyle and gastric shield (SCHELTEMA, 1978, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981b, 1988a). Such a condition reflects an increasing adaptation to specialised nourishment, moving away from micro-omnivory due to a less suitable distichous radula. This could point to an original carnivory in caudofoveate forerunners.

SIRENKO AND MINICHEV'S (1975) thesis of a monoserial origin of the placophoran radula is questioned by EERNISSE AND KERTH (1988), who underline a paired origin with three teeth at each side. Other molluscs may likewise show paired anlagen or even an initially distichous stage of the radula (KERTH, 1983, EERNISSE AND KERTH, 1988); this led to the assumption that a distichous type might have been the original radula of molluscs. All this supports carnivory as being original in contrast to the hitherto supposed herbivory. Accordingly, the primitive radula served to attack and split open soft-bodied prey. A monoserial elaboration of a midventral, serially chitinised pharyngeal cuticle as firm bars or flexible plates (see symphyses) — at each side elaborated to a definite cusp, denticle or hook — meets the conservatively

retained types in Solenogastres and most likely represented the original radula.

There is no mutuality with respect to the radula support. All Caudofoveata investigated possess a pair of elongate, well-delimited, compact bolsters which consist of muscular and connective tissue, frequently interspersed by turgescient or chondroid cells (e.g., WIREN, 1892, SCHELTEMA 1972). In Solenogastres a radula support frequently is represented only by some accumulation of muscular and connective tissue in median or paired arrangement. More differentiated supports consist of a distinct muscular concentration which may also include or be associated with turgescient cells (e.g., Amphimeniidae, Simrothiellidae; SALVINI-PLAWEN 1978, SCHELTEMA *ET AL.*, 1994). Occasionally (some Simrothiellidae), turgescient cells are very voluminous and distinctly arranged or may even be compacted to a pair of muscularly surrounded vesicles. Though such a latter condition resembles the radula vesicles of Placophora and Tryblidia (cf. WINGSTRAND, 1985), the exceptionality in advanced Solenogastres (Cavibelonia) clearly implies analogous similarity.

4. SYSTEMATICS OF SOLENOGASTRES

THIELE's classification of the Solenogastres (1913) — accepting four families with respect to the mantle cover and the presence/absence of respiratory organs (secondary gills) — had been abandoned by SALVINI-PLAWEN (1967) and replaced by a pure alphabetical order of the genera. Investigating an extensive material, SALVINI-PLAWEN (1978) then proposed a new classification based on the conditions of the mantle cover (orders, supraorders) and the various differentiation of the foregut glands and the radula (families). Accordingly, the representatives with a mantle cover of calcareous scales and of a thin cuticle, the order Pholidoskepia, are regarded as being conservative.

They are classified together with the Neomeniamorpha (with thin cuticle and spearlike, grooved mantle bodies, and with a highly complex accessory genital apparatus) as Aplotegmentaria. The small order Sterrofustia (thick cuticle; elongate, solid mantle bodies) and the order Cavibelonia (with acicular, hollow spicules and mostly with a thick cuticle) are classified as Pachytegmentaria. However, some findings raise the possibility that the formation of hollow needles (Cavibelonia) might be polyphyletic (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978, SCHELTEMA AND KUZIRIAN, 1991, HANDL AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2003).

To assess the phylogenetic interrelationships and evidence for the systematic arrangement of the families of Solenogastres, two character matrices for all genera were prepared and submitted to parsimony searches in PAUP* 4.0b10 (SWOFFORD, 2002). In addition to the Placophora and Caudofoveata, the taxon "Solenogastres" is included, defined by the putative plesiomorphic character states (when evaluable) or by "?" entries. Searches were limited to 750,000 shortest trees (using the command "set maxtrees") and 22 hours (using the *timelimit* option in the command *hsearch*), due to the high number of taxa and resulting trees as well as the limited computational resources. All searches hit the set number of trees, except for the weighted analysis for 53 characters which hit the time limit earlier.

(1) A matrix of 35 characters (1-35 in Tables II and III) at the level of presently accepted families was analyzed using unweighted and weighted parsimony (shortest trees of unweighted analysis: 88 steps, CI=0.3295, RC=0.2792). Both analyses yield largely unresolved strict consensus trees (not shown) with three major polytomies: the genera *Wirenia* and *Genitoconia* (part of Gymnomeniidae); the other Pholidoskepia including the "Solenogastres"; and all remaining advanced taxa. Among the latter, only Amphimeniidae and Rhipidoherpiidae appear monophyletic.

(2) Unweighted parsimony analysis of an enlarged matrix with 53 characters (Tables II and III) returned a similar strict consensus tree as analysis (1) (not shown; shortest trees: 161 steps, CI=0.2609, RC=0.2074). It separates only the Aplotegmentaria and the Pachytegmentaria. The basal Aplotegmentaria consist of a polytomy of 22 branches of Pholidoskepia (including "Solenogastres") with a common line for Gymnomeniidae, Acanthomeniidae, and monophyletic Neomeniamorpha. The advanced level of Pachytegmentaria represents a polytomy of 43 branches (e.g. Simrothiellidae in four lines), including the monophyla Amphimeniidae, Strophomeniidae, and Rhipidoherpiidae.

(3) In contrast, the majority-rule consensus tree (Fig. 8 A) is much better resolved. It separates the "Solenogastres" as the basal-most line from a polytomy of nine branches; seven of these represent most Pholidoskepia with monoserial radulae, one unites the Pholidoskepia with distichous radulae and the monophyletic Neomeniamorpha, and one leads to three dondersiid genera and to the Pachytegmentaria.

(4) The analysis of the 53-character matrix attributing the weight 5 to the characters 18 and 53 (Tables II and III) (shortest trees: 174 steps, CI=0.2874, RC=0.2303) returns an even better resolved majority-rule consensus tree (Fig. 8 B). It shows all Pholidoskepia with monoserial radulae in a basal polytomy, whereas those with distichous radulae are tied to the genera of the Sterrofustia, Neomeniamorpha, and Cavibelonia. Note that in this tree the Neomeniamorpha appear in an advanced position together with cavibelonian and sterrofustian genera.

The low number of characters available at the genus-level permits only limited resolution of the 87 ingroup taxa. First, the Pholidoskepia represent indeed the basal level among Solenogastres. Second, the Pholidoskepia with

monoserial radulae appear to be conservative compared with those with distichous radula. Third, the order Neomeniamorpha is confirmed to be monophyletic, though of doubtful relationship. Fourth, a polyphyly of the Cavibelonia is not visible in these trees; rather, a possible polyphyly is indicated for the Sterrofustia. Finally, only two families as presently defined are always monophyletic, the Rhipidoherpiidae and Amphimeniidae. Yet, in most majority-rule-consensus trees of the larger data set (Fig. 8 A, B), also Acanthomeniidae, Gymnomeniidae, Strophomeniidae, Epimeniidae and Proneomeniidae appear monophyletic.

It is evident that the "present: absent" coding (Table III) includes various convergencies (homoplastic characters) and most characters in the trees have low consistency indices (CI < 0.5). In some cases this implies unexpected results. Thus, in Fig. 8A, the lack of the terminal sense organ is a synapomorphy for three dondersiid genera (*Helluloherpia*, *Ichthyomenia*, *Heathia*) and brings them in a separate position, whereas the splitting of the Rhopalomeniidae is due to the foregut glands and the radula (in *Dinomenia*). Only the presence of the radula in *Dinomenia* isolates this genus from other Rhopalomeniidae in Fig. 8 B. The division of the Phyllomeniidae refers to the absence of the terminal sense organ in *Lituiherpia* and *Ocheyoherpia*. The latter condition unites these with the pararrhopaliid *Forcepimena*. The three families, Phyllomeniidae, Pararrhopaliidae and Rhopalomeniidae, however, due to the characters of the mantle cover, the radula and the foregut glands, appear not unexpectedly in an intermediate position between the Pholidoskepia and the derived Cavibelonia (see systematic arrangement in SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978). These examples demonstrate that the available characters are extremely homoplastic and that homology decisions are far too uncertain to accept the resulting trees as reflections of the phylogeny of the Solenogastres.

5. ANAGENETIC LEVELS IN MOLLUSCA

In view of the two different levels of elaborations of the midgut and the excretory system in Mollusca, the aplacophoran configurations are clearly more conservative than those of the Testaria (see also subradular organ, radular bolster): the respective elaborations express two subsequent evolutionary grades of molluscan organisation. This also holds true for the radula, which in both aplacophoran groups shows a conservative state with a "pre-ribbon" only (KERTH, 1983, WOLTER, 1992). Within Testaria, again two clearly different, subsequent grades are expressed, representing the polyplacophoran and the monoplacophoran (conchiferan) levels; this is also evidenced by cladistic analysis (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996, HASZPRUNAR, 2000). On one hand, the aplacophoran groups and Placophora share (as *Aculifera*) several conservative characters such as the chitinous cuticle with sclerites, a supra-rectal commissure, the heart-ventricle as a middorsal invagination of the pericardium and the paired muscle to roll up, or the plesiomorphic organisation of the ciliary apparatus (LUNDIN AND SCHANDER, 2001). On the other hand, Placophora and Tryblidia ("monoplacophorans") are closely interconnected by the almost identical organisation of the radular bolster (WINGSTRAND, 1985) and by the dorsoventral musculature. The monophyly of the monoplacophoran level (Conchifera), in turn, is manifested by the common differentiation of the shell or concha, of statocysts, of a sub-rectal commissure, of jaw plate(s), of a style-sack type of stomach and of cerebrally-innervated appendages (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1988A, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996, HASZPRUNAR, 2000).

The organ system that most clearly demonstrates the evolutionary pathway, however, is the mantle cover and its associated musculature. There is a name-giving, gradual anagenesis of the morphologically dorsal integument

(mantle, pallium) from the aplacophoran to the polyplacophoran and to the monoplacophoran (conchiferan) levels. The mantle in Solenogastres and Caudofoveata is homogeneously covered by a chitinous cuticle with embedded, unicellularly formed aragonitic sclerites, such as is also differentiated in the girdle or perinotum of Placophora. Evaluating the different kinds of elaborations shows that squamous elements or scales represent the most conservative types when compared with acicular spicules and other types of sclerites (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a, HAAS, 1981). This common character in aplacophoran and placophoran molluscs is paralleled by the *Musculus longitudinalis* along the mantle border; it rolls the animals up and is present in Solenogastres (*M.l.ventralis*) and in some lower Caudofoveata (*M.l.ventralis* in *Scutopus*) as well as in Placophora (*M.l.lateralis*; but see HASZPRUNAR AND WANNINGER, 2000). On the other hand, the homogeneously elaborated mantle — underlain by layers of outer transverse, intermediate oblique and inner longitudinal muscle fibres (such as in many other invertebrate groups) — in the aplacophoran level is strutted against the ventral body (foot) by a paired dorsoventral musculature. This is elaborated in an undefined number of serial pairs of two bundles, the dorsal-outer ones intercrossing medioventrally. In Placophora, the integumental musculature is restricted to bundles associated with the eight serial middorsal shell plates, whereas the dorsoventral musculature is concentrated (HASZPRUNAR AND WANNINGER, 2000) and grouped to 16 pairs of three bundles each, the dorsal-outer ones again intercrossing medioventrally. An identical configuration of dorsoventral musculature is present in Tryblidia. Here, however, every two successive bundle groups of the paired series are mostly fused into one common bundle. In the new monoplacophoran (or conchiferan) condition, the dorsoventral musculature is thus represented by eight, in part still subdi-

Figure 8. Maximum Parsimony analyses of Solenogastres genera according to 53 morphological characters (see Tables II and III). Note that due to the incongruency and low CI of most characters, these trees do not represent the phylogeny (see text). A: Majority-rule consensus tree of 750,000 most parsimonious trees returned by unweighted parsimony analysis of the 53-character matrix. B: Majority-rule consensus tree of 587,000 most parsimonious trees returned by weighted parsimony analysis of the 53-character matrix (weight 5 for characters 18 and 53).

Figura 8. Análisis de máxima parsimonia de generos de Solenogastres según 53 caracteres morfológicos (ver Tablas II y III). Nótese que debido a la incongruencia y al bajo CI de la mayoría de los caracteres, estos árboles no representan la filogenia (ver el texto). A: Árbol de máximo consenso de entre los 750.000 obtenidos por el análisis de parsimonia (misma importancia para todos los caracteres) de la matriz de los 53 caracteres. B: Árbol de máximo consenso de los 587.000 obtenidos por el análisis de parsimonia (peso 5 para los caracteres 18 a 53) de la matriz.

Table II. Characters to matrix in Table II (cf. THIELE, 1913; HOFFMANN, 1929; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1967, 1972b, 1978, 1985; SCHELTEMA, 1999, 2000; SCHELTEMA AND SCHANDER, 2000; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ, URGORRI AND CRISTOBO, 2000; HANDL AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001, 2003).

Table II. Caracteres de la matriz de la Tabla II (cf. THIELE, 1913; HOFFMANN, 1929; SALVINI-PLAWEN 1967, 1972b, 1978, 1985; SCHELTEMA, 1999, 2000; SCHELTEMA Y SCHANDER 2000; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ, URGORRI Y CRISTOBO, 2000; HANDL Y SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2001, 2003).

1	Cuticle: thin: 0, thick: 1
2	Shell plates: absent: 0, present: 1
3	Mantle bodies: scales: 0, other: 1
4	Acicular spicules: absent: 0, present: 1
5	Hollow needles: absent: 0, present: 1
6	Mantle bodies: one layer: 0, several layers: 1
7	Mantle bodies: hooks absent: 0, hooks present: 1
8	Mantle bodies : spear grooves absent: 0, present: 1
9	Foot: present: 0, absent: 1
10	Ctenidia: present: 0, absent: 1
11	Other respiratory organs: absent: 0, present: 1
12	Osphradia: present: 1, as dSO: 0
13	Subradular organ: absent: 0, present: 1
14	Midgut: not regionated: 0, regionated: 1
15	Gonoducts: present: 0, absent: 1
16	Aorta: absent: 0, present: 1
17	Sexes: separate: 0, hermaphroditic: 1
18	Ventral foregut glands: present: 0, absent: 1
19	Ventral foregut glands: type A: 0, other: 1
20	Ventral foregut glands: type B: 0, other: 1
21	Ventral foregut glands: type C: 0, other: 1
22	Ventral foregut glands: type D: 0, other: 1
23	Ventral foregut glands: follicular: 0, other: 1
24	Radula: present: 0, absent: 1
25	Radula: monoserial: 0, other: 1
26	Radula: monoserial plates: 0, other: 1
27	Radula: biserial: 0, other: 1
28	Radula: distichous: 0, other: 1
29	Radula: tetraserial: 0, other: 1
30	Radula: polystichous: 0, other: 1
31	Receptacula seminis: absent: 0, present: 1
32	Receptacula seminis: in bundles: 1, other: 0
33	Mucous tract glands; epithelial: 0, subepithelial: 1
34	Copulatory-stylet gland: absent: 0, present: 1
35	Commissural sack organ: absent: 0, present: 1
36	Dorsoterminal sense organ: present: 0, reduced: 1
37	Mouth and atrium: separate: 0, common/fused: 1
38	Copulatory stylets: absent: 0, present: 1
39	Secondary genital opening : paired: 0, single/fused: 1
40	Dorsal papilla foregut gland: absent: 0, present: 1
41	Peripharyngeal glandular organs: absent: 0, present: 1
42	Opening of ventral foregut glandular organs: sub-radular: 0, pre-radular: 1:
43	Midgut: without regular constrictions: 0, serial pouches: 1
44	Paired ventral radula sack: missing: 0, present: 1
45	Distally axe-shaped spicules: missing: 0, present: 1
46	Epidermal papillae: not elaborated: 0, present: 1
47	Buccal ganglia: present: 0, reduced/replaced: 1 (Epimenia)
48	gonoducts proper: present: 0, not elaborated: 1
49	Aorta: not elaborated: 0, present: 1
50	Aesthetes: not elaborated: 0, present: 1
51	Subradular sense organ: not present: 0, present: 1
52	Head-region: not elaborated: 0, separated: 1
53	Nail-formed spicules: absent: 0, present: 1

vided pairs of bundles (LEMCHE AND WINGSTRAND, 1959, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1969, 1981a, WINGSTRAND, 1985, HASZPRUNAR AND SCHAEFER, 1997a). Beyond this configuration of dorsoventral musculature, the almost identical organisation of the radular support likewise points to the polyplacophoran level as the direct forerunner of the monoplacophoran level by fusion of the eight shell plates towards the concha. This is also paralleled by the Merismconcha (YU, 1984, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991). In higher Conchifera, the dorsoventral musculature is even more concentrated (see also fossil *Cyrtoneida* and *Sinuitopsida*), resulting in a different number of paired bundles reflecting the shape and functional demands on the shell in each class.

Altogether, the mantle cover, the dorsoventral musculature, and the elaboration of the alimentary tract present successive, overlapping sequences of evolutionary differentiation. Within Mollusca they reflect a distinct, gradual anagenesis from the aplacophoran to the polyplacophoran and monoplacophoran (conchiferan) levels. These evolutionary grades also indicate the direction in which the homology series must be read and defined. This clearly reveals the Solenogastres and Caudofoveata to be early, conservative offshoots of the molluscan organisation (rather than being derived from polyplacophorans). It likewise excludes a monophyly of *Aculifera* (e.g. SCHELTEMA, 1996, IVANOV, 1996), which would incorrectly assume the above-presented coincidences in the alimentary tract and the excretory system in Testaria to be convergencies; it also removes most of the potential synapomorphies from the Solenogastres and Caudofoveata (revealing them to be plesiomorphies).

6. PLESIOMORPHIC CONDITIONS OF MOLLUSCA

The evaluation of plesiomorphic characters in Mollusca and of the original molluscan organisation yields two

results: it summarises the smallest common denominators of features, and it traces the anagenetic conditions back to their most basic elaboration.

Within the conservative level of aplacophoran molluscs, the Caudofoveata exhibit, in some characters, more advanced conditions than Solenogastres. Of particular interest are the protostyle formation in the midgut, an aorta, a radula ribbon and ctenidia — all also present in Testaria. Are these characters synapomorphies or merely convergent autapomorphies in Caudofoveata and Testaria (or simply reduced in Solenogastres)? Cladistic computer programs, due to their reflection of numerical taxonomy, use the parsimony argument to incorporate them as synapomorphies and make the Solenogastres the earliest offshoot (cf. SALVINI-PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996, HASZPRUNAR, 2000). The elaboration of a midgut section with a protostyle and gastric shield among Caudofoveata has been verified in the most advanced Chaetodermatidae only, but the functional parallelism of this elaboration is obvious (see also MORTON, 1960, for similar differentiations in other animal groups). Conversely, the adaptive flexibility of the circulatory system throughout Mollusca casts doubt on aorta formation as being a strong synapomorphic character rather than a functionally-tied, convergent differentiation. As outlined above, the light-optically recognized radula membrane in Caudofoveata is a kind of pre-ribbon, but intermediates between the elaborations in Solenogastres and Placophora. This may reflect either a synapomorphic or a convergent differentiation of a true ribbon and thus weakens the argument. With regard to the ctenidia and their characteristic elaborations (see SALVINI-PLAWEN 1981a, 1985, HASZPRUNAR, 1987), they are generally accepted to be a typical molluscan character and hence proposed to be already differentiated in the common forerunners (archimolluscs). Their absence in Solenogastres, either within monophyletic aplacophorans or as a sister-group of Tes-

is known from development, the differentiation of gonads as a rostral elongation of the pericardium, with retroperitoneal incorporation of the primary germ cells, appears to be a key character of Mollusca (gono-pericardium). The same conditions are found, e.g., in Siphonopoda ("cephalopods") and Bivalvia-*Anodonta*, which retain the interconnection between pericardium and gonads. In addition, the late anlage of separate gonoducts (apart from pericardioducts) in Placophora and Siphonopoda-Coleoidea (HIGLEY AND HEATH, 1912, HOFFMANN, 1937), as well as the variable gonoduct formation in Conchifera (RAVEN, 1958), suggest that the gonoducts are relatively young or new differentiations (with genetically weak determination), and may be polyphyletic among Testaria. Accordingly, the configuration in both Solenogastres and Caudofoveata could represent a true plesiomorphy (not yet developed gonoducts) or a paedomorphy (retention of developmental stage). The presence of true gonoducts in Solenogastres-*Phyllomenia*, due to the much altered configuration of the pericardioducts and spawning ducts (cf. SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978), could represent a specialisation (autapomorphy) within that genus; it is thus *per se* not conclusive (see also Haszprunar, 1992). Yet, the possible secondary loss of gonoducts in Solenogastres-*Driomenia* (HEATH, 1911, HOFFMAN, 1949) lends weight to the *Phyllomenia* argument. If, on the other hand, the lack of gonoducts is truly a secondary loss (as more generally assumed), due to the independently narrowed body in Solenogastres and Caudofoveata, this reduction would then reflect analogously acquired adaptations or parallelism (rather than a synapomorphy).

The narrow, ciliated pericardioducts of Caudofoveata often unite abruptly via a sunken opening into the paired glandular duct or sack (e.g., HEATH, 1905: 721); only the latter are connected to the mucous tracts of the mantle cavity, into which they open ventrolaterally by means of a sphincter. These glandular organs often extend beyond the

pericardioduct opening (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a), be it rostrally (e.g., *Prochaetoderma californicum* Schwabl, 1963) or dorsally (e.g., *Scutopus robustus*; Fig. 2); in immature *Scutopus ventrolineatus* S.-Plawen, 1968, the glandular sacks show a dorsoventral extension, with the sunken pericardioduct openings located centrally. In contrast, the pericardioducts in many Chaetodermatidae open axially into the dorsoterminally bent glandular ducts. Due to our lack of information on organogenesis, the homology of these glandular ducts remains unclear. With respect to their totally different histology (HEATH, 1905, 1911, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a, SCHELTENA ET AL., 1994), to the often sunken opening of the pericardioducts, and to the anterior extension beyond this opening, the glandular ducts do not appear to be part of the mesodermal pericardioducts. According to their position (see Fig. 2), they would more probably represent a rostral, internalised portion of a formerly paired mantle groove (devoid of mucous tracts). However, their own lateroventral (instead of frontal) opening into the mucous tracts, and the elaboration of these openings as narrow pores with a distinct sphincter, makes such an interpretation dubious. This also holds true for the exceptional configuration in *Prochaetoderma californicum*, in which the mucous tracts form tubes being closed up from the medial mantle cavity (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a: Abb. 27F). Alternatively, the glandular ducts could be remains of the original gonoducts into which the pericardioducts opened to form a common outlet. This interpretation (HOFFMANN, 1937, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a) suffers from the condition that such common outlets in various bivalves and gastropods are generally characterised by the openings of gonoducts into lower pericardioducts (excretory organ or duct), rather than pericardioducts into lower gonoducts.

Hermaphroditism is characteristic for Solenogastres and Gastropoda-Euthyneura, though it also occurs in other molluscan groups (not known in

Figure 9. Preoral trochi (prototrochs) in Bivalvia. A: pericalymma larva of *Yoldia limatula* with three trochi (from DREW, 1901); B stenocalymma larva of *Mactra chinensis* (ventral view) with three trochi (from MEDVEDEVA AND MALAKHOV, 1983); C pseudotrochophora (praeveliger) larva of *Pandora inaequivalis* (lateral view) with two trochi (after ALLEN, 1961).

Figura 9. Cilios preorales (prototrocas) en Bivalvia. A: larva pericalymma de *Yoldia limatula* con 3 hileras de cilios (de DREW, 1901); B: larva stenocalymma de *Mactra chinensis* (vista ventral) con tres hileras de cilios (tomado de MEDVEDEVA Y MALAKHOV, 1983); C: larva pseudotrocófora (preveliger) de *Pandora inaequivalis* (vista lateral) con dos hileras de cilios (de ALLEN, 1961).

Caudofoveata and Siphonopoda/cephalopods). Among organisms with separate sexes, free external fertilisation in the open water appears to be primitive, conservatively also correlated with so-called ect-aquasperms ("head" of short nucleus with conical acrosomal vesicle and 4-5 round proximal mitochondria, a diplosome and abruptly separated flagellum). Internal fertilisation implies alteration of sperm organisation and shape (introsperm). Once specialised, no reversal to aquasperm is possible. This also holds true if separate sexes are secondarily acquired; a case in point are the Microhedyllidae (Gastropoda-Opisthobranchia-Acochlid-iomorpha), which use spermatophores (summarised by E. Wawra in ARNAUD, POIZAT AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1986). Caudofoveata and Placophora possess somewhat modified aquasperms, whereas the hermaphroditic Solenogastres exhibit highly derived introsperms (SCHELTEMA ET AL., 1994, HEALY, SCHAE-

FER AND HASZPRUNAR, 1995). As evidenced by the outgroup comparison (cf. HEALY ET AL., 1995), the hermaphroditism and introsperms of Solenogastres clearly appear to be autapomorphies for this class.

The larval development of lower groups within molluscan classes (apart from Siphonopoda/cephalopods) includes lecithotrophic trochus larvae (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1980, 1991; HASZPRUNAR, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND RIEGER, 1995). Among these, Solenogastres show the pericalymma and stenocalymma types (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991, OKUSU, 2002) and Caudofoveata the stenocalymma type (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991, NIELSEN, 1995). Both these types are also present in lower Bivalvia (Fig. 9), and stenocalymma in Scaphopoda, whereas the larvae of Placophora and most Archaeogastropoda (without larval shell) possess the pseudotrochophora or praeveliger type only (FIORONI, 1982, SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991, HASZPRUNAR ET

AL., 1995). Larvae, however, are ecologically-conditioned and many are provided with a trochus or other similar features. Unfortunately, this had led such larvae to be inaccurately termed "trochophorae" (ROUSE, 1999). Not only is this in contrast to the original definition (HATSCHKE, 1891), but it disregards the detailed morphological differences necessary for homologisation (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1980), i.e. neglecting analogies (see also HASZPRUNAR, 1995). Note that all known Solenogastres larvae possess one preoral trochus only. In contrast, other free-living pericalymma and stenocalymma types of Caudofoveata, Bivalvia and Scaphopoda exhibit three preoral trochi (NIELSEN, 1995, OKUSU, 2002). Based on the sequence of pericalymma (*Nematomenia*, *Neomenia*, etc.) to stenocalymma (*Epimения*) in Solenogastres and Bivalvia (Fig. 9), and even an individual transition from pericalymma to stenocalymma in *Epimения* (Solenogastres-Cavibelonia; OKUSU, 2002), the pericalymma type appears to be the conservative one (rather than the pseudotrochophora type). The outgroup comparison (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1980, HASZPRUNAR ET AL., 1995) supports this view.

There are only few, more general developmental coincidences between Mollusca and Coelomata (spiral cleavage, endomesoblast 4d, trochus larvae of pericalymma rather than "trochophora" type; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1988b); such coincidences do not pertain, however, to the configuration of the body cavity. The formerly heavily discussed theory of a coelomate nature and metameric segmentation in Mollusca, renewed with the one-sided interpretation of Tryblidia organisation (LEMICHE AND WINGSTRAND 1959), is now obsolete (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1969, 1981a, 1988b, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND BARTOLOMAEUS, 1995, HASZPRUNAR AND SCHAEFER 1997a, HASZPRUNAR AND WANNINGER, 2000). The dorsoventral musculature in Placophora, arranged in 16 pairs of bundles, ontogenetically differentiates from a multiple serial condition similar to that in recent Solenogastres, and the anterior (pre-trochal) mus-

culature recapitulates a "worm-grid" (HASZPRUNAR AND WANNINGER, 2000). Moreover, the developmental fate of the (endo-) mesoblastema in Placophora (musculature, pericardium) and spiralian Coelomata (secondary body cavity, musculature) is distinctly different (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND BARTOLOMAEUS, 1995), negating any mutual dependence of the derivatives. Underlined by the organisation of Solenogastres (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND BARTOLOMAEUS, 1995), the molluscan forerunners most logically originated from epifaunal, ciliary-gliding mesenchymate to pseudo-coelomate Spiralia (TRUEMAN, 1976).

With regard to the plesiomorphic conditions of Mollusca, the comparative consideration of the two diphyletic recent taxa of paraphyletic *Aplacophora* clearly helps to outline the probable original organisation of molluscs (archimolluscs). This, in turn, provides a common base for understanding the subsequent phylogenetic radiation. The plesiomorphies include (comp. also SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972a, 1981a, 1985, 1991, HASZPRUNAR, 1992):

- A dorsoventrally constructed body with separation into a ventral locomotory surface in the form of a ciliary gliding sole (foot) and a dorsal protective surface (mantle); the latter secretes a chitinous cuticle as well as unicellularly formed, squamous calcareous sclerites (aragonitic scales).
- Foot and mantle at least in posterior part of body separated by a peripodal groove (pallial cavity) with body outlets, high glandular mucous tracts and (?) one pair of ctenidia.
- A paired chemoreceptive (osphradial) sense organ between the terminal mantle rim and pallial cavity, innervated from the suprarectal commissure.
- An amphineurous nervous system consisting of a paired cerebral ganglion, buccal ring and two pairs of medullary body nerve cords irregularly interconnected by ventral (pedal) commissures and lateroventral connectives; lateral cords with suprarectal commissure.
- A subintegumental musculature below the mantle consisting of outer

transverse, intermediate oblique and inner longitudinal fibres, the latter reinforced lateroventrally below the lateral rim of the mantle.

- Without segmentation, but with serially arranged dorsoventral musculature of two pairs of bundles between mantle and foot, the dorsal-outer ones intercrossing medioventrally.

- An alimentary tract only subdivided into foregut and body-filling midgut without separate gland organ(s).

- A monoserial radula formed of serially-midventrally chitinised pharyngeal cuticle and consisting of firm or flexible plates, at both sides each with lateral cusp, denticle or hook; not yet differentiated radula membrane (ribbon).

- Associated with the radula, a paired glandular organ of subepithelial follicles (without paired duct?).

- A suprarectal pericardium with middorsal heart invagination having a single ventricle and a paired auricle (atrium), the latter also performing ultrafiltration (for the primary urine).

- A mesenchymate-pseudocoelomate body cavity with an open circulatory system without aorta.

- Paired pericardioducts without excretory function (no formation of secondary urine).

- A paired gonad differentiated and separated as a rostral enlargement of the pericardium (gono-pericardium); type of gonadial outlets not yet clarified.

- Sexes separate, free fertilisation by means of aquasperms.

- Spiral cleavage

- Indirect development through leci-thotrophic trochus larvae of pericalymma type.

- Epibenthic carnivores feeding on more or less immobile, soft-bodied prey.

CONCLUSIONS

A serious, comparative consideration of the aplacophoran molluscs, despite the limited state of knowledge, reveals much important information, particularly with respect to the

phylogenetic discussion. Their organisation, especially the different elaborations of mantle cavity organs, clearly reflects the presence of two distinct taxa, the Solenogastres (neomeniomorphs) and the Caudofoveata (chaetodermomorphs). They evolved as diphyletic clades from the common molluscan bed (archimolluscan stem group), which clearly belonged to the aplacophoran level. Thus, *Aplacophora* is paraphyletic, also including the common molluscan ancestors, and the coincidences between the diphyletic Solenogastres and Caudofoveata appear to reflect mere symplesiomorphies. The relative position of both these taxa to the Testaria, however, still remains to be clarified. In any case, characters of the recent Solenogastres and Caudofoveata must be taken into consideration when seriously discussing molluscan plesiomorphies and the archimolluscan organisation.

The characters treated above point to originally mesenchymate-pseudocoelomate organisms with epifaunal, ciliary locomotion; these ancestors most probably nourished themselves as carnivores on soft-bodied, fairly sessile prey (rather than having been algae-scraping herbivores). Such an acoelomate, ciliary-gliding organisation clearly points to an origin from a likewise ciliary-gliding group of organisms with spiral cleavage (possibly close to kamptozoan tholophora larvae; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1980; HASZPRUNAR *ET AL.*, 1995, HASZPRUNAR, 1996, 2000); these organisations subsequently differentiated molluscan characters (dorsal protective cover, mantle cavity, heart within pericardium, radula). There is no indication at all that the molluscan ancestors had a coelomate organisation (i. e. with secondary body cavity). The pericardium and subsequent gono-pericardium appears to be an autapomorphic adaptation for the new heart, which served for body-fluid circulation and ultrafiltration, i.e. to compensate a restricted distribution of metabolites due to the novel mantle cover and the concentration of gas exchange at the posterior body (mantle

cavity). In contrast, the common stock of related coelomate Spiralia most probably originated as a sister-group by acquiring a secondary body cavity: emerging from the same acoelomate ciliary-gliding forerunners, they adapted to an infaunal, burrowing habit (CLARK, 1964). The rounding up of the body yielded a worm-shaped form with loss of ciliation, which was subsequently followed by the autapomorphic formation of a body-filling hydrostatic coelom, i.e. the secondary body cavity. (Among such monophyletically evolved coelomate Spiralia, the sipunculids with their benthosphaera larvae may perhaps

have retained conservative traits; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1988b, SCHELTEMA, 1996, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996, BOORE AND STATON, 2002.)

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